

BETWEEN STATUES AND ICONS

ICONIC PERSONS FROM ANTIQUITY TO THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES

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In this book, Vladimir Ivanovici focuses on the so-called iconic state of humans in Antiquity, Late Antiquity, and the early Middle Ages. This iconic state is defined as a capacity attributed to human beings for rendering the divine visible through their bodies. This iconic state was considered desirable by the inhabitants of the Roman Empire. It influenced Roman culture from the reign of Octavian Augustus (27 BC–AD 14) to Justin II's (AD 565–574) reign. The appearance of this iconic state was made possible through the historical process of Rome's ascendancy to world rule, leading to a favorable redefinition of man's place in the cosmos, allowing for the possibility of attaining immortality. As such, the anthropological model of iconicity is considered unique to Roman society and appears in different specific contexts. The shifting relationships between three interacting categories, namely iconic persons, cult statues, and other objects (relics, icons, eulogia), are studied in an epoch that saw the shift from paganism to Christianity.

In the first chapter, Ivanovici describes the different tendencies present in the early Empire, allowing for the later appearance of iconicity. With the underlying notion that the human body was considered capable of disclosing a person's character, persons under the early Empire had different strategies available to attain immortality, either through performing extraordinary military feats, through the deifying effect of virtues, or initiation rituals allowing for a close following of the gods. These strategies reflected on the human body, which took over the gestures and vocabulary associated with cult statues. These tendencies prepared for the appearance of imperial iconicity, which was the dominant form of (late) antique iconicity described in Chapter 2.

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We see that the imperial self-representation as divine constituted the leading barometer and catalyst of the tendency to credit humans with iconic potential. This form of iconicity will trigger, through the persecution of Christians refusing to comply with the imperial cult, the appearance of the iconicity of martyrs (Chapter 3). It will be the benchmark for other competing and interacting forms of iconicity (Chapters 4-6). The main strategies for accomplishing imperial iconicity were the use of visual media (with the looks of emperors approaching the looks of Gods and vice versa), the use of imperial portraits, and the rulers' physical appearance and behavior, leading to a popularized view of the emperor as a living cult statue. Ivanovici stresses that this evolution towards imperial iconicity started in the early imperial period and resulted in a genuine belief in the emperor's own divinity rather than being a premeditated political strategy. As such, the reforms of the emperor Diocletian (AD 242-312) stressing the emperor's divine status were an update of the office and ritual to the *Zeitgeist*. In a Christian empire, emperors became a living image of Christ within an increasingly hierarchical society. The early Byzantine society saw the iconicity of the ruler fully institutionalized so that it passed from the ruler's person to the artifacts surrounding him, annulling the individuality of the emperor, and resulting in emperors living in a state of self-isolation. Although this process behind imperial iconicity was already described in previous literature, the novelty of Ivanovici's analysis lies in stressing how this iconicity was shaped by statue worship and how it had its roots in an earlier period.

In Chapter 3, Ivanovici shows how the iconic category of the martyrs played a crucial role in the shifting relationships between iconic persons and surrounding objects. Once Christian martyrdom became an empire-wide phenomenon, the Christian communities felt the need for a common denominator for martyrs. This was found in the luminosity and sturdiness of their bodies, which became markers of the

theophanic quality of martyrs like cult statues. After the persecutions, the image of Christ was sought in other categories than martyrs, which resulted in different persons, such as bishops, baptizands, consecrated virgins, and desert ascetics, inheriting martyrs' iconicity through an imitation of Christ. Furthermore, the iconic quality of martyrs was transferred to their relics, making inanimate matter and the sacred places where these relics were deposited as a medium for interacting with the divine. Whereas previous research considered the fourth century to change the Christian relationship with the material world significantly, Ivanovici shows this was part of a linear process with continuities in earlier periods.

The luminous iconicity of the martyrs was grafted on the splendid imperial iconicity in the iconicity of initiates (Chapter 4). Some important sacred texts, such as the Book of Genesis describing the first human Adam as an image of God and the metaphor of "putting on Christ" in the works of the Apostle Paul (ca. AD 5-65), furthered a strong analogy between the iconicity of baptizands and cult statues. In this vein, clergy and parents considered lay people and children chiseled to Christian perfection, respectively. The possibility for everyone to achieve iconic status through baptism led to a negatively perceived dilution of the image of God. This dilution was countered by the distinctive aspects of the iconicity of bishops (Chapter 5).

The episcopal iconicity (Chapter 5) was diverse because of cultural and theological differences in the empire. In the West, bishops looked to the bishop of Rome as a model and developed their iconicity with the support of new rulers and with Roman and early Byzantine models in mind. Homogenizing religious practices under Emperor Justinian (AD 482-565) made bishops local images of imperial iconicity in the East. This resulted in the replacement of the imperial cult by a Christian alternative. With the emperor's cult statue replaced by living bishops, the episcopal iconicity in the East was

thoroughly subjected to imperial iconicity.

The iconicity of the stylites (Chapter 6) powerfully expresses the anthropological model under scrutiny, as it combined the iconic dimension of ascetics with a setting referencing imperial iconicity, the iconicity of Christ, and integration in the clergy. As living statues, stylites made explicit the principle of iconic people competing with the role of cult statues. With the dissemination of tokens related to stylites, the iconic quality was transferred to inanimate matter in the same way as relics.

In summary, the book traces the history of iconic persons acting as vessels and an image of the divine. In this history, the association and analogy with cult statues were made, at first unconsciously, later consciously. The different manifestations of iconicity were not perceived as part of the same phenomenon in previous research. However, Ivanovici shows these manifestations rose from the same background and developed in mutual dialogue and competition. In a startling continuity, the conditions that made competition between living persons and cult statues possible for iconic status are to be sought in the early imperial period. The iconic person became a focus for Christian and other religious communities in the later Roman Empire. Iconic persons became naturalized in the fifth century, and their power was transferred to artifacts, such as the imperial insignia, martyr relics, episcopal cathedrae, and the tokens of stylites. As such, objects took center stage and filled the space statues had occupied in private devotion. The traumatic events of the seventh century led to a loss in confidence and a concomitant change in self-perception. As a result, iconicity became reserved for the afterlife or religious overachievers.

The book gives a good synthesis of an anthropological trend. It shows how so-called late antique developments are, in fact, to a high degree, natural developments of phenomena present in the early imperial period. It succeeds in integrating different cultural phenomena in one framework, which was grounded in

antiquity and had imperial iconicity as its benchmark. As such, the global overview and synthetic approach make the book highly relevant and accessible to both a scholarly audience and a larger public. The analysis has an excellent combination of literary sources and a vast array of material sources, showing the rich iconographic traditions of (late) antiquity. Furthermore, the vast array of material sources shows how the anthropological trends described in the book permeated all aspects of (late) antique visual culture.

However, a book with a generalized bird's eye view inevitably imposes a construct on the complex historical reality, leading to some (minor) inadequacies. Firstly, the book presumes a general trend unique to the Roman Empire and made possible by its privileged position as a world power on the (late) antique geopolitical scene. However, in my opinion, this is not proven without a sustained comparative approach. More specifically, a comparison with the Roman Empire's respected adversary, the Sassanian Empire (AD 224–651), would have furthered the argument. Secondly, I have the impression that the author underestimates the reach of conscious individual human agency in favor of the blind inevitability of an anthropological process. Notably, in the realm of imperial iconicity, one can assume a greater measure of conscious individual image building - for example, interpreting the reforms of Diocletian as a mere update of the office to *Zeitgeist* does injustice to the novelty of the Tetrarchy. Thirdly, there is the problem of chronology. As the book takes a bird-eye view of human behavior in its interaction with the divine, I would consider the perspective of the *longue durée* to be suitable. For example, why not, when speaking of the iconicity of the ruler, take a short fast forward to the evolution of this iconicity in the Medieval West, up until the abrupt destruction of this iconicity with the beheading of Louis XVI of France (21/01/1793) and the subsequent abolishment of the Holy Roman Empire in 1803? Why not mention the

subsequent evolutions of this iconicity under the Ottoman Sultans after the fall of Constantinople? Indeed, the author casually takes on this perspective, referencing later periods, such as Sultan Bayezid I (1360-1406) and Tamerlane (1336-1405). However, any serious pursuit of this *longue durée* perspective is absent, even in the book's concluding sections, which are, to my feeling, rather succinct. At the same time, the author is bent on defining a terminus for the phenomena he describes, mentioning either the reign of Emperor Justin II (565–574) or the death of Emperor Anastasius I (ca. AD 431- AD 518). I believe these different ending dates do not further the otherwise compelling argument and cause unnecessary confusion.

In sum, despite some minor inaccuracies, *Between Statues and Icons: Iconic Persons from Antiquity to the Early Middle Ages* is an enjoyable read with high relevance for readers looking to plunge themselves into the anthropology behind the Romans' interaction with the divine (Late) Antiquity and the early Middle Ages.

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